

Practical application of the Ayurvedic treatment system

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Being one of the oldest medical systems, Ayurveda had a great influence on the development of world medicine. Even in ancient times, Indian medicinal plants were transported by sea and land trade routes to Parthia, the countries of the Mediterranean and Central Asia, the basins of the Caspian and Black Seas, and Southern Siberia and China. The main export items were spikenard, musk, sandalwood, cinnamon, aloe and other plants, and incense. The treatise “Ashtanga Hridaya Samhita”, written in the 4th century. BC e. formed the basis of the treatise on Tibetan medicine by Zhud Shi. Jurisprudence began to penetrate into the region of Tibet from the 7th century . n. e., when one of the representatives of the Bharadwaja school became the personal physician of the ruler of Tibet, Songtsen Gampo.

During the heyday of the Abbasid Caliphate, many doctors from India worked in Baghdad, some of whom enjoyed influence at the court of the Caliph. Mathematical, medical, including pharmacological and Juverdic texts (among them Sushruta Samhita) were translated into Arabic in Baghdad at the end of the first millennium AD ry. It is likely that our great philosopher and physician Abu Ali Ibn Sina used the Arabic translation of the treatise (“Ashtankar”) when writing the “Canon of Medical Science.” Subsequently, Ibn Sina’s texts were studied by European alchemists, whose works had a significant influence on the formation of European medicine and chemistry.

In the 17th century East India Company surgeons studied the art of rhinoplasty from Ayurvedic doctors. In the XVIII-XIX centuries. Ayurveda experienced a decline, unable to withstand competition with European doctors.

By the middle of the 20th century. Together with the fashion for Eastern esoteric practices, traditional Indian medicine gained popularity in the West, and with the beginning of perestroika - in Russia. In the United States, legal science is studied at the National Institute of Ayurvedic Medicine (founded by Scott Gerson); in Israel - at Reidaman College, founded by Sally Reedman. Students study for 4 years, and upon completion of their studies, an internship is carried out in India.¹

At present, in India, traditional medicine is being studied under the general guidance of the Central Council for the Research of Ancient Indian Medicine and Siddha (CCRAS), which includes the national There are scientific research institutes. ²The Government of India has established two research centers for work in the field of A legal science. More than 150 associations and centers, as a rule, at medical colleges, study various aspects of ancient teachings using modern methods. A university has been founded in the city of Jamnagar, Gujarat state, where they train specialists and researchers in the field of law . There are several pharmaceutical companies that produce Ayurvedic and Unani medicines under the control of the government. In India and Sri Lanka, Ayurveda doctors study for 5.5 years and pass a state exam. This is a complete

¹Sorokina T. S. History of medicine . – Russia, 2009. – P. 213.

² Kovalev S.A. Ancient Indian systems of medicine . – Russia, 2020. – P. 87.

bachelor's degree program and is taught in many Indian and several Sri Lankan universities. It includes four and a half years of study and a year of practice in the hospital.

In addition to India, Ayurveda is used in Nepal and Sri Lanka. According to The Himalayan Times, in Nepal, legal medicine is used by 75-80% of the population and is the most common form of medicine in the country.³

The World Health Organization has recognized Ayurveda as an effective alternative system of medicine. In many countries around the world, Ayurveda universities offer the study of the Ayurvedic system of treating various diseases. The Ayurveda system is effective for almost all diseases of the human body. It is closely connected with nature, because... All drugs are prepared from natural components that have proven their effectiveness for many years and have no side effects.

“This medical system considers the connection between a person and the entire Universe. Since childhood, every person has five elements - space, air, fire, earth and water. Their compositions form 3 doshas - the three main principles of the work of the Universe: Vata is space and air, Pitta is fire and water, Kapha is water and earth.”

According to Ayurveda, doshas replace each other twice in a day - these are biorhythms. Each of the three dominates in a specific season of the year and in a person's age. The constitution of the body, emotional state, temperament, mental abilities, and character depend on them.

“It is believed that health rests on three pillars - sleep, nutrition, behavior. Food that is not suitable for the body type, time of day, season and age, a daily routine that does not coincide with the biorhythms of nature - all these are causes of imbalances that lead to serious diseases aniyam. The disease develops in six stages. And only the latter reaches the physical level - when it is possible to do tests and make a diagnosis. In Ayurvedic diagnostics, the imbalance can be corrected at the initial stage, and with the help of nutrition, regimen, and the use of natural herbal preparations, the disease can be stopped. The goal is rather not treatment, but prevention⁴. ”

Another principle is to treat not the disease, but the whole person. This is called a holistic approach. Therefore, different herbs, medications, exercises and procedures are prescribed to different people, depending on the dosha, in order to restore balance to a particular body.

Complex equipment and laboratory technologies are not used in the production of Ayurvedic medicines. To isolate the active components of plants in the manufacture of medicine, as a rule, water, vegetable or ghee is used, and the resulting products are consumed in the form of ordinary powders, etc. tablet. Chemical preparations are never used to isolate active components, which ensures the purity of the final product and the absence of residual chemical substances that can cause harm. Some ingredients used in Ayurvedic remedies are toxic in their raw, unprocessed form, so they are boiled until the toxic properties completely disappear. Now cough has become a very common problem. Ayurveda has in its arsenal effective medicinal plants that help get rid of cough.

According to research, approximately a fifth of food remains undigested. Toxins are formed that accumulate in tissues. The disease does not come suddenly - it matures over months and years, and it cannot be cured with one tablet.

³Scott W. You searched for Weeklong program to observe Health Day // The Himalayan Times, 2015. – P. 20.

⁴<https://lite.mir24.tv/articles/16422732/ayurveda-kak-drevnyaya-medicinskaya-sistema-rabotaet-v-sovremennom-mire>

One of the principles of Jurisprudence is detoxification of the body to restore balance. This is already closer to a way of life, and not to therapy: proper food, absence of bad habits, daily routine.⁵

For example, Indian folk medicine recommends going to bed before 10 pm and getting up before 7 am. Modern science says that for resting the body, the most effective sleep is from 22 pm o 24 hours Intermittent fasting, which is popular today, is also one of the foundations of jurisprudence.

Serious diseases using this medical practice are treated only in medical centers in India, Sri Lanka, and the Maldives. They try to resort to medications as a last resort. In our country, when they talk about yurveda , they mainly mean massages, yoga, cosmetic masks, work with herbs, oils, and incense. Among the drugs, only numerous dietary supplements (biologically active additives) are found in Uzbekistan.

Food is a kind of conductor between a person and the outside world. There is even a whole set of nutritional rules that are followed by those who practice Ayurveda. For example, you need to adhere to the principle of food compatibility - consume fruits, starch, proteins and fats separately, at different times of the day. You should definitely include all six tastes in your diet: sweet, salty, sour, astringent, spicy, bitter.⁶

Golden milk. This is the name of the drink, which, in addition to milk itself, contains turmeric, honey and various spices. It is believed that it has rejuvenating, nourishing, anti-inflammatory properties, and removes toxins. If you add ground ginger, cinnamon and vanilla, then drink it warmed up at night, you can enhance its beneficial properties. This drink not only gives strength, but also helps solve some problems with the skin and metabolism.

Another drink that is on the menu of almost everyone who practices Indian medicine is ginger water. To prepare it, boil several rings of the root of this plant. It is recommended to drink it for colds, weather sensitivity and to help remove toxins and waste from the body.

Various types of massage, acupuncture, aromatherapy have proven themselves well through many years of experience and are very popular among the population. The achievements of modern pharmacology can and should be combined with the heritage of healing practices known from the beginning of civilization. But an indispensable condition is the availability of medical education for persons engaged in non-traditional medicine.

Thus, the medical science of Ayurveda is based on assigning a special role to prevention, immunity, harmony with oneself, which is achievable with the unity of life guidelines, thoughts, feelings and actions, balance between the human personality and nature as the totality of all manifestations of existence.

At present, interest and the use of folk and traditional medicine are significantly increasing all over the world due to its effectiveness and accessibility. The desire for integration observed in modern medicine and the official acceptance of the expediency of using traditional medicine practices make it possible to open up prospects for widespread use knowledge of Ayurvedic medicine, its safe and productive methods and remedies in everyday medical practice and maintaining public health.

⁵Fedoseeva T. Great encyclopedia of body cleansing. Life and health. – Russia , 2006. – P. 286.

⁶Agarwal V., Abhijnhan A., Raviraj P. Ayurvedic medicine for schizophrenia // Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews. Issue 4. – GB : London , 2007. – R. 255-256.

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Ayurveda studies the general principles of human structure (metaphysical anatomy), the laws of normal functioning of the human body (normal physiology), mechanisms of disease development neither (pathogenesis), methods of maintaining health, and other disciplines common to all people.⁷

But, at the same time, Ayurveda proclaims the uniqueness of each individual person, recognizes the presence of individual psycho-physiological characteristics: genetics, internal personality, structural features of the body and organs, metabolism features, immunity, strength, endurance, temperament, emotionality, stereotypes of thinking and much more. All these individual psycho-physiological characteristics are described by the Ayurvedic constitution of a person, the current ratio of doshas and his mental constitution.

Thus, Ayurveda implements its general principles taking into account the individual psycho-physiological characteristics of the patient in specific external circumstances: the patient's place of stay and current time (season of year, age period of the patient's life, etc.).

The individual approach of Ayurveda is implemented in all areas of its activity: diagnosis, prevention and treatment of diseases. For example: modern medicine and Western herbal medicine widely use hawthorn tincture in the treatment of heart failure. Ayurveda in this situation acts more selectively: it takes into account not only the diagnosis, but also the individual psycho-physiological characteristics of the patient, which are described by his Ayurvedic knowledge constitution. Thus, hawthorn can be used in the treatment of heart failure in people with dominant Vata and Pitta doshas. But, hawthorn will not be used in a Pitta-type patient, since along with the benefits for the heart, this plant will have a negative effect on other organs and systems of a person with a dominant Pitt a-doshey.⁸

⁷Articles by A. Ya. Semiryazhko: Essays on Ayurveda https://ayur-fresh.ru/blog/category/a_semiryazhko_blog

⁸Egorov G. Ayurveda. Women's problems. – Russia: Sattva, 2011. – P. 25.